

USING DIFFERENT METHODS FOR TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO MIXED AGED GROUP

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Annotation. In this article, the information is given about the education of in our country and the approaches of teaching mixed ability classes.

Key words. Well-educated, gap, fulfill, handful, methodology.

Introduction. Nowadays, knowing the English language is becoming the need of the time. A person who can not be considered as well-educated if he does not know any foreign languages, especially English. More and more people attend language courses to fill this gap in their education and also many educators try to find the ways of making the learning process easier, more active, sufficient and less time-consuming for mixed ability classes. The choice of the appropriate method in teaching is considered among professional teachers to be an essential factor, especially for second language learning. Early on during our placement studies we were made aware of the challenge of teaching – what we have experienced to be – large and multilevel classes. In my opinion, the fact that classes in English are heterogeneous with, for example, a great span of proficiency among students, can be tricky for a teacher, due to the fact

that English as a subject not only involves communication in English as a tool for learning, but also as one of the main learning objectives. How can a teacher meet the needs of the different students in this type of class so that they are all appropriately challenged and their various needs as learners met? It is often said that the instruction of students in school is mostly located at the level where a majority can keep up well, and thus disregards the ones who would benefit from instruction at other level. However, research shows that it is important that the level of instruction is adapted to the student for learning to take place, and it is hence vital that teachers practise an instruction that is differentiated.

Literature review. Determining what constitutes a multilevel class is not easy, according to Hess (2001); since no learner is exactly the same in terms of for example proficiency, aptitude and learning style, all classes could be described as being multilevel. For Hess a multilevel class has been created on the basis of age, irrespective of the students' level of proficiency or ability as learner. While Hess recognizes that there are challenges to teaching a multilevel class, she also finds that there are many advantages. One of them is that students are able to help each other out, which is a huge asset indeed in a large class with only one teacher (Hess, 2001). In accordance with the well-known Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) theory about learning by Vygotsky (in Strandberg, 2006), there is great potential in a mix of students since less able students can accomplish more with support from more advanced ones. Another advantage with many different students is that they can contribute with many different aspects, such as opinions and experiences, resulting in an interesting learning environment (Al-Subaiei, 2017; Hess, 2001) something that the curriculum Lgr 11 (Skolverket 2011), too, describes as an advantage. A huge challenge for a teacher in a multilevel group is to find a level of instruction that is not too challenging for the students that are on a more basic level and that still manages to keep the interest of the more advanced learners (Bell, 2001). For what happens to learning if the level of instruction does not fit the individual student? Motivation is often said to be the engine of learning (Stensmo, 2008).

Teaching has always been regarded as an art because there has never been one best way to teach something and, it has never been as easy as using one best way to educate someone. Teaching does not mean using only one textbook and fulfilling all exercises orderly in the given textbook and I think, if it was so simple like "a one fits all" approach anyone could be a teacher in our society. However, it is a common situation that, there are no students that are absolutely alike and there are no students learning absolutely the same way, even though the curriculum may be the same.

To be honest, teaching or educating someone is not as easy as most people thought and it makes teachers research more, learn new information, create something to attract learners. But in most cases they follow only one strategy where the educators have a tendency to give a lecture about something, but it usually does not work for all students (especially, visual learners who are good at learning something easily by seeing new information), they continue using this approach instead of making or responding to students' need. On the contrary of these teachers, there are some educators who use and follow differentiated instructions, methods, approaches to meet the needs of mixed ability learners.

Most of the teaching in our country is lecture oriented and the instruction is teacher based. The students are not active participants in the learning process. The worst sufferers are the little children in the pre-primary level. Though a handful of private schools in the large cities practice a certain method for teaching, it serves to cater to a selected few and the majority are left to suffice with an unplanned, random and haphazard system of teaching. In a country where the literacy ratio is alarmingly low, there is no systematic methodology adopted to foster learning in the early years. The system does not have a programme for the preschool years, which are so vital for the overall development of the child. Until recently it was not even officially considered part of the education process.

Despite these many benefits, however, mixed age groups come with some challenges. Some teachers struggle with the increased demands of attending to a differentiated group. They may benefit from additional classroom support and access to a wide range of resources. There are several strategies that may help teachers get the best out of their special group. Here are a few:

1. Get to know your students. Become acquainted with their likes and dislikes, their personalities, and their differing levels of ability. The more you know your students the easier it will be for you to create the activities, tasks, assignments and lessons that engage them best.

2. Value their individual needs. To the best of your ability, define your teaching goals by the abilities of your students rather than their age. If you are able to value the different stages and paces in your classroom, your students will be more successful, and your job, less stressful.

3. Allow older students to assist younger students. The benefits are multifold: the older student gets an opportunity to reinforce his/her own skills while learning social responsibility; the younger student benefits from the guidance, and also benefits from a sense of community. In addition, the teacher benefits from getting "assistance" while everyone is learning something valuable.

4. Consider each lesson topic from multiple angles. Your lessons should take all age groups and abilities into consideration. Instead of planning separate lessons for separate age groups, gather age-appropriate material geared towards the same theme or subject. Worksheets for a lesson on the life of ants, for example, may include a sheet of fill-in-the-blank ant-related sentences for older students at the early reading level, and a worksheet of matching pictures to ant-related words for students still grasping the first skills of reading.

5. Plan games and crafts that everyone can enjoy. Games and crafts are excellent opportunities for all students to relax, learn through play, release stress and increase confidence. Assign leadership roles to older students or think of ways to make their specific tasks more challenging.

Conclusion. It's worth nothing that organizing and implementing differentiated education requires a lot of time and work . It necessitates careful lesson planning on the part of the teacher. However, once teachers are comfortable with using different levels of activities for different levels of pupils , they will discover that their time is well spent and that their students respond positively.

Differentiated instruction is cyclical process of learning about the learners and differentiating accordingly. It is found on the notion that teaching methods should be varied and altered to meet the needs of individual and diverse group of students in class. It means that in order to provide the finest learning experience possible, teachers must reach out to an individual or small group to modify their teaching . As a result , differentiated instruction requires flexibility in their teaching approach and also good teaching requires differentiation , which is a necessary component of effective instruction and teaching.

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